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NORMS OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE

Annotation

This work proves that speech occupies a huge part of our lives. All people have to influence others, but the ability to influence features is important when success depends on the ability to clearly express your thoughts, to convince others of the correctness of your point of view. An active, responsible life position allows you to improve the ability to simultaneously know, think, be able to express your thoughts, prove and defend your own opinion. In this, a person is helped by the language and culture of speech - the beginning of all beginnings.

Key words: Speech etiquette, speech culture, literary language, word shades, stable communication formulas, humanitarian disciplines, signs of speech etiquette.

НОРМЫ РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА

Аннотация

Данная работа доказывает, что речь занимает огромную часть нашей жизни. Всем людям приходится влиять на окружающих, но умение влиять особенно важно, когда успех зависит от способности ясно излагать свои мысли, убеждать окружающих в верности вашей точки зрения. Активная, ответственная жизненная позиция позволяет совершенствовать способность одновременно знать, думать, уметь выразить свою мысль, доказать и отстаивать собственное мнение. В этом человеку помогает язык и культура речи — начала всех начал.

Ключевые слова: Речевой этикет, культура речи, литературный язык, оттенки слова, устойчивые формулы общения, гуманитарные дисциплины, признаки речевого этикета.

НУТҚ ОДОБИ МЕЪЁРЛАРИ

Аннотация

Мазкур мақолада нутқ маданияти ҳаётимизнинг катта қисмини эгаллаши ва у инсонлар бир-бирларига таъсир ўтказишида, фикрларини аниқ ифодалашда, бошқаларни ўз нуқтаи назарининг тўғрилигига ишонтиришида муҳим аҳамият касб этиши яна бир бор исботланди. Нутқ маданияти фаол, масъулиятли ҳаётий жараёнда билиш, фикрлаш, ўз фикрларини ифода этиш, ўз фикрингизни исботлаш ва ҳимоя қилиш қобилиятини оширишга имкон беради. Бу борада одамга тил ва нутқ маданияти ёрдам бериши ҳақида мақолада фикр юритилади.

Калит сўзлар: Нутқ одоби, нутқ маданияти, адабий тил, сўз белгилари, барқарор мулоқот формулалари, гуманитар фанлар, нутқ одоби белгилари.

Introduction. Language is the most important means of human communication; it is an instrument of thought. Therefore, it is important for people to remember that not only knowledge of the matter can bring them success, but also how they master the culture of speech, which means mastering the norms of oral and written literary language.

All human life is closely connected with language. Since childhood, people have been studying their native speech, meeting new words and expressions. They carefully treat their own and other people's speech, understand all the shades of the word well, we all must master the culture of speech - this is our common, important task. Any person is obliged to strive for a high culture of speech, to treat their native language with care. Grammatically correct pronunciation, stress, reasoning and correctness of a person's speech with semantic content, not only in the process of publicly expressing one's views, but also when solving business issues over the phone.

Literature review. Speech etiquette is a set of requirements for the form, content, order, nature and situational relevance of statements accepted in a given culture. The well-known researcher of speech etiquette N.I. Formanovskaya gives the following definition: "Speech etiquette is understood as the regulatory rules of speech behavior, a system of nationally specific stereotyped, stable communication formulas accepted and prescribed by society

to establish contact between interlocutors, maintain and interrupt contact in the chosen key." Speech etiquette, in particular, includes words and expressions used by people to say goodbye, requests, apologies, forms of address adopted in various situations, intonation features that characterize polite speech, etc. The study of speech etiquette occupies a special position at the intersection of linguistics, theory and history of culture, ethnography, regional studies, psychology and other humanitarian disciplines.

Research Methodology. The broad concept of culture certainly includes what is called the culture of communication, the culture of speech behavior. To own it, you need to understand the essence of Russian speech etiquette. In communication, people transmit this or that information, certain thoughts to each other, communicate something, encourage something, ask about something, perform certain speech actions. However, before proceeding to the exchange of logical and meaningful information, it is necessary to enter into speech contact, and this is done according to certain rules. We hardly notice them, because they are familiar. It is just the violation of the unwritten rules that becomes noticeable: the seller addressed the buyer with "you", the acquaintance did not say hello at the meeting, they did not thank someone for the service, and they did not apologize for the misconduct. As a rule, such non-fulfillment of the norms of speech behavior turns into an insult, and even a quarrel, a conflict in the team.

Therefore, it is important to pay attention to the rules for entering into verbal contact, maintaining such contact - after all, business relations are impossible without this. It is clear that awareness of the norms of communication and speech behavior is useful to everyone, and especially to people of those professions that are associated with speech. These are teachers, doctors, lawyers, service workers, businessmen, and just parents. The rules of speech behavior are regulated by speech etiquette, a system of set expressions that has developed in language and speech, used in situations of establishing and maintaining contact.

These are situations of appeal, greetings, farewell, apologies, gratitude, congratulations, wishes, sympathy and condolences, approval and compliments, invitations, suggestions, requests for advice, and many others etc. Speech etiquette covers everything that expresses a benevolent attitude towards the interlocutor, which can create a favorable climate for communication. A rich set of linguistic means makes it possible to choose a form of communication that is appropriate for the speech situation and favorable for the addressee "you" or "you", establish a friendly, relaxed or, conversely, official tone of conversation.

Thus, the choice of the most appropriate expression of speech etiquette constitutes the rules for entering into communication. Using the expressions of speech etiquette, we perform relatively simple speech actions, address, greet, thank ... But why are there so many ways in the language to do this? After all, we have up to forty expressions used in greetings, many forms of farewell, gratitude, etc. And how many opportunities to fulfill the request: I ask you to do this; Please do not make noise; Do it please; If it's not difficult for you, move over, please; Could you move over?; Is it difficult for you to move?; Don't have something to write down? - And so on up to forty models. In addition, the thing is that we choose each expression taking into account who - to whom - where - when - why - why says. Therefore, it turns out that complex linguistic social information is embedded just in speech etiquette to the greatest extent. Let's ask ourselves why the expressions of speech etiquette have "magic power", why their correct use brings satisfaction to people, and failure to perform in the right situation leads to resentment? It seems that there are several essential features of speech etiquette that explain its social acuteness. The first sign is associated with the unwritten requirement of society for the use of signs of etiquette. If you want to be "one's own" in a given group - large or small, national, social - perform the appropriate rituals of behavior and communication. The social purpose of ritual signs of etiquette is brought up in people from early childhood. The second sign is related to the fact that the performance of signs of etiquette is perceived by the addressee as social "stroking". The third important feature of speech etiquette is that the pronunciation of an etiquette expression is a speech action, or a speech act, that is, the performance of a specific task with the help of speech.

The fourth feature is related to the third and concerns the very structure of statements in which "I" and "you" are open: I thank you; Excuse me. This is an open, explicit representation of the communicants in the grammar of the sentence, but there can also be a hidden, implicit, semantic representation of them, as in gratitude Thank you or sorry, which, due to synonymy, functional equivalence with those presented earlier, contain in the deep structure the "I" of the speaker and "you" of the addressee (I tell you) thank you.

The fifth important feature of speech etiquette can be considered its connection with the category of politeness. On the one hand, politeness is a moral quality that characterizes a person for whom showing respect for people has become a familiar way of communicating with others as a daily norm of behavior. On the other hand, it is an ethical category

abstracted from specific people, which is also reflected in the language, which, of course, should be studied by linguistics.

The sixth sign is related to the fact that speech etiquette is an important element of the culture of the people, a product of human cultural activity and an instrument of such activity. Speech etiquette, as can be seen from the foregoing, is an integral part of the culture of human behavior and communication. In the expressions of speech etiquette, social relations of a particular era are fixed.

Analysis and results. A modern person must have a certain culture and behave correctly at work with the people around him: with visitors (with cents), subordinates and bosses. To do this, he must speak correctly. There are certain rules, the main ones are as follows:

Talking to a person should be polite and even voice;

You must be willing to talk to the person;

The conversation should be friendly; You should only be in a good mood;

When talking, you should look into the eyes of your interlocutor affably and attentively; you cannot look away;

It is impossible during a conversation to grimace, twist your mouth, wrinkle your forehead and nose - this not only offends the interlocutor, but also makes you funny;

Do not interrupt or interrupt the interlocutor - it seems that you do not respect him;

Whatever your interlocutor says, you must listen to the end. You can interrupt it only for personal reasons or in the case when the monologue you listen to is beyond the bounds of decency;

No need to slap the interlocutor on the shoulder, push him, poke his finger in the stomach or twirl the buttons on his jacket;

No need to gesticulate with your hands or fingers, roll your eyes, etc., as it seems that you do not have enough vocabulary and you are an uncultured person;

"The art of speaking is the art of silence", so at first listen; do not litter your speech with parasitic words;

You should not express yourself too intricately, using a large number of foreign words, emphasizing your education. Many will not understand you, but you will be funny to those who know;

try to speak clearly, slowly, do not mumble or swallow words and their endings; intonation - a form of pronunciation of words and sentences - should not be offensive to a person and not offensive to him.

A good conversationalist is an attentive listener who, without interrupting, listens respectfully and is genuinely interested in what they are told. To become a good interlocutor, you must adhere to some rules:

Refer to the interlocutor only by name;

You need to be able to speak correctly with your interlocutor;

Your conversation should convince your interlocutor of his importance as a person;

You need to be a good conversationalist;

The topic of conversation should be interesting and useful to your interlocutor;

You must smile at people. What does it mean to be able to persuade a business partner to your point of view and influence him so that he does what is necessary in your interests, while respecting his own interests, that is, it is the ability to find a common language with your partner. In communication between people, and especially between business people, there are often situations where their opinions are ambiguous and grounds for conflict between them may arise. In these situations, one of the parties may win, some compromise may be found, or perhaps no acceptable solution will be found. To avoid this unpleasant situation, it is advisable to use certain tips, the observance of which will help convince people and persuade them to their point of view.

Let us turn to these tips: Before you start complex business with your little-known business partner, you need to study the features of his character. The only way to win an argument is to avoid it altogether. Show respect for the opinion of your interlocutor and never tell him that he is wrong. If you are wrong, admit it quickly and decisively. From the very beginning of the conversation, keep a friendly tone. Try to get your interlocutor to immediately answer you "yes" several times at the beginning of the conversation. Let your interlocutor do most of the talking, and you listen carefully without interrupting.

Try to convince your interlocutor that this idea belongs to him. Sincerely try to look at things not only from your own interests, but also from the point of view of your interlocutor (business partner). Be sympathetic to the thoughts and desires of others. Appeal to nobler motives. Do not dramatize your ideas, present them effectively. Do not challenge, touching a nerve. Let us highlight a few more points about talking to a person. Formulas of speech etiquette the basis of speech etiquette is speech formulas, the nature of which depends on the characteristics of communication. Any act of communication has a beginning, main part and final part.

Conclusion/Recommendations. Summing up, we can say that the possession of competent and correct speech is one of the foundations of successful communication. However, it is expediently impossible to build one's speech without knowledge of ethical speech norms. Etiquette and culture of speech are the rules adopted in a particular society, circle of people, norms of behavior, including speech, which, on the one hand, regulate, and on the other hand, reveal, show the relations of members of society. Without knowing these rules, a person is not able to find a common language with members of society. It is especially important to know the speech norms in business communication.

In addition, without knowledge of elementary, but so important norms and rules of etiquette, in particular speech, success is impossible. Etiquette, if understood as a set order of behavior, helps to avoid mistakes or smooth them out in accessible, generally accepted ways. Therefore, we can conclude that compliance with speech norms is an integral quality of a cultured and successful person. To master literate speech, you must, first, master the basic principles of speech etiquette and learn generally accepted speech norms.

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